

doi:10.5281/zenodo.16937125

Performance and Retention of Physics Concepts Among Senior Secondary Students: A Comparative Study of Expository and Guided-Inquiry Laboratory Strategies

¹Prof. Fidelis A. Onwioduokit & SAM, Uduakobong Edet²

Department of Science Education,
University of Uyo, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

¹Email: fidelisonwioduokit@uniuyo.edu.ng; ²Email: uduakobongsam@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study was carried out to examine the comparative effect of Guided-Inquiry and Expository Laboratory strategies on Senior Secondary School Physics Students' Performance and Retention, focusing on the concept of Simple Harmonic Motion (SHM). Three research questions were raised and three null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The study adopted Quasi-experimental design using non-randomized pretest and post-test group. The population consisted of all the 998 senior secondary two Physics students during 2023/2024 academic session in all the 10 public secondary schools in Itu L.G.A., Akwa Ibom State. A sample size of 220 respondents were selected using Purposive sampling technique. The research had four intact classes; two intact classes each from the urban and rural locations. One group each from the urban and rural locations were taught using guided-inquiry method while the other group were taught with expository method in both locations. One researcher-made instruments titled 'Physics Performance Test (PPT) was used for data collection for students' performance (pre-test, post-test and retention test). The instrument was faced and contents validated by three validators in from the University of Uyo and a reliability coefficient of 0.85 was obtained using Test-retest method. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer all the research questions and Analysis of Covariance was used to test all the hypotheses at .05 significant level. The findings of the study showed a significant difference in the academic performance of Physics students taught with Guided-Inquiry and those taught using expository methods. The finding also showed a significant difference in the in students' retention in physics when taught SHM with Guided-Inquiry and Expository methods. The findings also showed a significant difference in the mean retention between male and female Physics students taught SHM with guided-Inquiry and Expository methods. Based on these finding of the study it was concluded although guided-inquiry is a student-centered method which is highly recommended in modern days learning. And that the observed disparity between male and female students could be traced to factors like students' interest. It was recommended that physics concepts like Simple Harmonic Motion should be taught with suitable teaching method and preferably student-centered methods like Guided-Inquiry as it enhances effective learning and retention among students.

Keywords: Expository Laboratory strategies, Guided-Inquiry, Physics Students

INTRODUCTION

Physics Education refers to the teaching and learning of physics concepts, theories, and principles. It encompasses formal education in schools and universities, as well as informal education through outreach programs, self-study, and online resources (Hazari 2021). Physics education is crucial for nurturing critical thinking skills and scientific literacy among students, particularly at the senior secondary level. Laboratory practical sessions are integral components of physics education as they provide hands-on experience and reinforce theoretical concepts (Demirci, 2017). However, traditional laboratory setups often face constraints such as limited equipment availability, safety concerns, and time constraints, which can hinder students' engagement and learning outcomes. According to Singh (2020) physics education is a tool for enhancing science teaching need to be reinvigorated for total over hauling in education sector and modern technology. For Physics to be taught properly and effectively, laboratories must be an integral part of the Physics curriculum.

The human brain is wired to forget not all information is needed beyond the immediate moment or situation. It's up to instructional designers and training facilitators to help learners maximize knowledge retention. On this note Prince (2021) defines retention as the ability to remember experiences and things that had already been learned. It is the process in which material or information preciously learns or material is brought back all over again to awareness. Learning retention is a person's ability to transfer new information into their long-term memory so that it is easy for them to recall and put that knowledge to use in the future. In simpler words, learning retention is all about making new knowledge stick for a long time. Retention of scientific concepts, especially in Physics, remains a fundamental challenge in science education due to the abstract nature and mathematical demands of the subject. Many secondary school students struggle to recall previously taught Physics concepts, leading to poor performance in subsequent topics and standardized examinations (Ogunleye and Ayodele, 2021). According to Adebayo and Oladeji, 2020 Effective learning, comprehension, and retention of physics concepts are closely linked to key elements such as the teacher's subject matter expertise and the instructional strategies employed during classroom delivery.

The commonly used Expository teaching method, which is predominantly teacher-centered and emphasizes information transmission, is often criticized for encouraging rote learning and passive student involvement (Udo and Udofia, 2021). While it may lead to immediate learning gains, it frequently fails to support long-term retention of scientific concepts, as students do not engage meaningfully with the learning process. The expository laboratory teaching method is a traditional instructional approach where the teacher or instructor guides students through a structured lab activity, with clearly defined steps and expected outcomes. In this method, the focus is on delivering content through direct instruction and demonstration, where students follow prescribed procedures to achieve predetermined results. This approach is often used in science education to help students learn specific techniques, concepts, or principles by replicating experiments with known outcomes, which helps in reinforcing theoretical knowledge through practical application (Sadeh and Zion, 2021). In expository laboratory approach, the teacher typically provides a detailed lab manual or set of instructions, and students are expected to follow these steps closely without deviating or exploring alternative methods. This approach is beneficial for introducing complex techniques or ensuring safety in experiments, as students have clear instructions to minimize errors or hazards. However, critics argue that it can limit student creativity and critical thinking since it often discourages inquiry or experimentation beyond the prescribed activities (Hake, 2020). Conversely, the Guided-Inquiry instructional method promotes active learner engagement by encouraging exploration, questioning, hands-on experimentation, and teacher-guided facilitation. Recent studies have shown that inquiry-based learning enhances cognitive processing, which significantly improves students' ability to retain and retrieve knowledge over time (Adesoji and Jimoh, 2021; Yusuf and Onasanya, 2020). Inquiry based laboratories are separated into two groups as guided inquiry and open inquiry. Students build scientific understanding more effectively when they engage in hands-on, student-centered, and open-ended activities, which are fundamental components of the guided-inquiry approach. This method encourages active participation and critical thinking. Recent research by Eze, Ofoegbu, and Ukoha (2020)

found that guided-inquiry instruction significantly improved students' learning outcomes and enhanced long-term retention in science subjects. In guided inquiry laboratory method, student search for an experiment through the given problem. In this method, the experiments are similar with the expository experiments, but a lab manual is not given to the students. Students search for the experiment process and reach scientific information through the experiment. Guided inquiry laboratory settings encourage students to make scientific research and consider science as careers (Hendrickson, 2015). The constructivist basis of Guided-Inquiry encourages students to build their own understanding, which is more likely to be retained (Bruner, 1961).

The word gender is a psycho-analytic concept, which stressed the sociological roles and cultural responsibilities of men and women (masculine and feminine) in the society. According to Wang and Degol (2017), gender refers to the socially culturally constructed characteristics and role which are ascribed to male and female in the society. Human beings belong to masculine and feminine gender while non-living things belong to neuter gender. Student's gender refers to those characteristics of male and female students that is socially determined and is always distinguished from those that are genetically or biologically determined, called sex (UNESCO, 2023). Gender is a series of awareness of being male or female within a culture. The issue gender is of great importance in science education especially with increasing emphasis on the ways of boosting manpower for technology and development as well as increasing the population of females in science and technology fields (Almalki & Alghamdi, 2023). Gender has long been a point of discussion in relation to students' achievement in science education, as inconsistent research findings have continued to fuel debates among educators and researchers. While some studies report no significant differences in science performance between males and females, others highlight disparities favoring one gender over the other. The ambiguity in findings suggests that gender-related performance in science remains inconclusive. These disparities are influenced by various socio-cultural, psychological, and pedagogical factors. Despite ongoing interventions aimed at fostering gender inclusivity in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM), gender gaps in science education remain a challenge (Okeke and John, 2021). Understanding the underlying issues and challenges is crucial for addressing gender inequities and fostering inclusive learning environments. Gender disparities in science education are evident in participation rates at various educational levels. Research by Wang and Degol (2017) found significant gender gaps in science achievement and interest among students, with boys outperforming girls in standardized tests and expressing greater interest in science-related careers. Gender disparities in science education are often reinforced by persistent stereotypes and implicit biases that shape learners' self-concepts and academic interests. These biases can subtly influence how students perceive their capabilities and determine their willingness to pursue science-related careers. Recent studies suggest that the association of science and technical fields with masculinity continues to discourage many female students from fully engaging in STEM disciplines (Cheryan et al., 2017).

A more recent study by Adewale and Ogunleye (2021) investigated the impact of instructional strategies on students' science achievement across urban and rural schools. Their findings showed that students taught using guided discovery methods outperformed their peers who were taught with traditional lecture approaches, indicating a significant improvement in knowledge acquisition among those exposed to active learning strategies. Also, Oladipo and Abimbola (2020) examined the effectiveness of guided discovery learning on secondary school students' achievement in science subjects in Kwara State, Nigeria. Using a quasi-experimental design with a sample of 240 Senior Secondary School students, the researchers employed a validated 30-item Science Achievement Test as their primary data collection instrument. The findings showed that students taught using the guided discovery method significantly outperformed those taught through conventional methods. The study concluded that guided discovery enhances conceptual understanding and promotes active engagement in science learning. Nwoye et al. (2020) explored gender differences in academic retention among Senior Secondary School students taught electrostatics using a Computer Animated Instructional Package (CAIP) in the Awka Education Zone of Anambra State, Nigeria. The quasi-experimental non-equivalent control group design involved a sample

of 68 SS I students selected through multistage sampling from a population of 3,438 students. The Electric Charge Electric Field Achievement Retention Test (ECEFART), with a reliability index of 0.89, was used for data collection. Data were analyzed using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at a 0.05 significance level. Results indicated that gender had no significant influence on students' retention in electrostatics when taught with CAIP, and there was no significant interaction effect of treatment and gender on academic retention. The study recommended the use of computer-animated packages to enhance retention in physics, irrespective of gender. *The study carried out by Sam and Stephen (2025) to examine the effect of PhET Simulation technology and gender on secondary school Physics students' academic performance in Uyo Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. The study adopted Quasi-experimental design using non-randomized pre-test post-test control group. The population consisted of all the 3,183 senior secondary one Physics students during 2023/2024 academic session in all the 15 public secondary schools in Uyo L.G.A., Akwa Ibom State. A sample size of 202 respondents was selected using Purposive sampling technique. The findings of the study showed a significant difference in the academic performance of Physics students taught with PhET Simulation technology and those taught using expository method. The finding showed a no significant difference in the performance of male and female Physics students taught with PhET Simulation technology and a no significant difference also exists in the academic performance of urban and rural Physics students taught with PhET Simulation technology.*

Despite these insights, most classroom instruction in Physics in Nigeria still relies heavily on expository strategies, and the comparative effects of these methods on students' retention of Physics concepts remain underexplored. A direct comparison of these strategies could provide teachers and curriculum developers with evidence-based practices for improving science learning outcomes.

Statement of Problem

While considerable research has been done on the effect of teaching methods on academic performance, there is relatively little focus on how these strategies influence students' retention of Physics concepts over time. Report from WAEC showed that there is an increasing poor performance among candidates who took the WAEC examination for the past years. Given the persistent underperformance of students in Physics and the widespread use of traditional teaching approaches, it is essential to investigate which method better supports long-term understanding. The researcher found it imperative to investigate on which approach between Guided-Inquiry and Expository approaches encourage the retention of physics concept in secondary schools.

Purpose of the Study

The objectives of this study are stated below:

- To compare the mean performance of Physics concepts among students taught using Guided-Inquiry and Expository laboratory strategies
- To compare the retention of Physics concepts among students taught using Guided-Inquiry and Expository laboratory strategies.
- To determine the influence of gender on the retention of Physics concepts among students exposed to Guided-Inquiry and Expository strategies.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised:

1. What difference exists between the mean performance scores of Physics students taught the concept of Simple Harmonic Motion using Guided-Inquiry and those taught with Expository laboratory strategies?
2. What difference exists the mean retention scores of Physics students taught the concept of Simple Harmonic Motion using Guided-Inquiry and those taught with Expository laboratory strategies?
3. Is there a significant difference in the mean retention scores between the male and female students taught with Guided-Inquiry and Expository laboratory strategies?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance.

Ho₁ There is no significant difference in mean performance of Physics concepts between students taught using Guided-Inquiry and those taught with Expository strategies

Ho₂ There is no significant difference in retention of Physics concepts between students taught using Guided-Inquiry and those taught with Expository strategies

Ho₃ There is no significant difference in mean retention scores between the male and female students taught with Guided-Inquiry and Expository laboratory strategies.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a quasi-experimental non-equivalent control group design, which involved pretest, posttest, and retention test. Four intact classes were used, two assigned to the Guided-Inquiry laboratory group and the other two the Expository laboratory group. This research design was appropriate because it enabled the researcher to investigate the effects of instructional strategies in real classroom environments without manipulating group assignments, thereby preserving the natural setting while still assessing causal relationships (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). The study area was Itu Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Itu Local Government is one of the Ibibio tribes in Uyo Senatorial District of Akwa Ibom State with a land mass of approximately 606.1 square kilometers. It is under Itu- Ibiono Ibom Federal Constituency and was created in 1987. The Local Government is bounded in the North and North East by Odukpani in Cross River State and Arochukwu in Abia State respectively. In the West by Ibiono Ibom and Ikono Local Government Areas, in the South and South-East by Uyo and Uruan Local Government Area respectively. The population of the study cut across 998 senior secondary two physics students, the sample size for the study was 220 Senior Secondary two Physics students purposely drawn from the 10 public secondary schools from the area. Below were the criteria for school selection:

- Schools with at least one qualified physics teacher
- Available Laboratory
- Comparable performance in an external examination (WAEC and NECO)

One researcher-made instruments titled: Physics Performance Test (PPT) developed on the concept of Simple Harmonic motion for pretest, posttest and retention. The PPT was made of 50 multiple-choice items, each carried 2 marks. The maximum score for the instrument was 100 marks. In order to establish the reliability of the instrument; the PPT was administered to 20 physics students who were not part of the main study by using Test-retest method, the reliability coefficient of 0.85 was gotten after analyzing the scores with Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). The instruments were considered highly reliable for data collection for the study.

Experimental Procedure

The experiment lasted six **weeks**, divided as follows:

- **Week 1:** obtaining permission from the participating schools administrators and the administration of the pretest for both groups.
- **Weeks 2–3:** Teaching of the concept of SHM to the two groups, one group were taught the concept of SHM using Guided-Inquiry while the other group were taught with the Expository Laboratory by the help of the Physics teacher who served as the research assistant. Immediately after the teaching(treatment), the posttest was administered to all the groups.
 - The **Guided-Inquiry group** engaged in hands-on investigations and teacher-facilitated teaching with probing questions.
 - The **Expository group** received structured lectures and demonstrations with detailed explanation of the concept, immediately after the treatment the posttest was administered to all the groups.
- **Week 4-6:** Administration of Retention test and scoring. The retention test was a reshuffled version of the instruments PPT administered three weeks after the posttest.

Data Collection and Data Analysis

Data were collected separately by administering the PPT on SHM as pretest to students before treatment. After treatment, the posttest was administered and a reshuffled version of the instruments were

administered three weeks after the posttest as retention test, they were marked and score as a single test and the scores used for analysis; mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What difference exists between the mean performance scores of Physics students taught the concept of Simple Harmonic Motion using Guided-Inquiry and those taught with Expository laboratory strategies?*

Table 1.1 Mean and Standard Deviation of Pre-test and Post-test Scores of Students Performance in Physics taught using Guided-Inquiry and those taught using Expository Method.

Strategy	N	PRETEST		POSTTEST		Mean Difference
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	
Guided-Inquiry	112	29.77	7.11	64.86	14.30	35.09
Expository	108	29.28	9.80	58.11	10.25	28.83

The result in Table 1.1 shows the pre-test and post-test mean scores of students taught Physics with Guided-Inquiry strategy are 29.77 and 64.86 with their respective standard deviations of 7.11 and 14.30. The result further shows the pre-test and post-test mean scores of students taught using expository strategy of 29.28 and 58.11 and their respective standard deviations of 9.80 and 10.25 respectively. This shows that there was a higher performance in the post-test scores of the two groups but students taught with guided-inquiry has the highest mean difference of 35.09 against 28.83 of the expository group. This means that from the study, the those taught with the guided-inquiry method performed better than those taught with expository method but in all groups, it showed that learning had taking place.

Research Question 2: *What difference exists the mean retention scores of Physics students taught the concept of Simple Harmonic Motion using Guided-Inquiry and those taught with Expository laboratory strategies?*

Table 1.2 Mean and Standard Deviation of Post-test and Retention Scores of Students Performance in Physics taught using Guided-Inquiry and those taught using Expository Method.

Strategy	N	POSTTEST		RETENTION		Knowledge Retain (%)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	
Guided-Inquiry	112	64.86	14.30	55.52	12.01	85.60
Expository	108	58.11	10.25	48.03	12.14	82.65

The result in Table 1.2 shows the mean post-test and retention scores of experimental students taught Physics with Guided-Inquiry are 64.86 and 55.52 with their respective standard deviations of 14.30 and 12.01. The result further shows the mean of post-test and retention scores of students taught using expository method of 58.11 and 48.03 and their respective standard deviations of 10.25 and 12.14 respectively. The retention rate of students taught with both guide-inquiry and expository methods are 85.60% and 82.65% respectively which showed that the student still retained some knowledge on the

concept but there is high retention of knowledge from students taught with Guided-Inquiry method than those taught with Expository method.

Research Question 3: *Is there a significant difference in the mean retention scores between the male and female students taught with Guided-Inquiry and Expository laboratory strategies?*

Table 1.3 Mean and Standard Deviation of SS II Male and Female Students taught Physics with Guided-Inquiry and Expository Methods

Strategy	Gender	N	POSTTEST		RETENTION		
			Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	Knowledge Retain (%)
Guided-Inquiry	Male	51	65.20	14.29	56.14	11.77	86.10
	Female	61	64.57	14.42	55.00	12.28	85.18
Expository	Male	61	57.43	9.97	47.90	12.62	83.41
	Female	47	59.00	10.65	48.19	11.62	81.68

The result in Table 1.3 showed the mean post-test and retention scores of male students taught Physics with Guided-Inquiry 65.20 and 56.14 with their respective standard deviations of 14.29 and 11.77 while the female means scores of 64.57 and 55.00 and their respective standard deviation of 14.42 and 12.28. For students taught with Expository method, the mean score of 57.43 and 47.90 with standard deviations of 9.97 and 12.62 for post-test and retention respectively. While their female counterpart had mean of 59.00 and 48.19 with the standard deviation of 10.65 and 11.62 respectively. The result further shows the percentage of knowledge gained by students taught with guided-inquiry (male= 86.10% and female = 85.18%) and that of students taught with expository (male = 83.41% and female = 81.68%). This shows that the male students in the guided-inquiry group and expository group retained knowledge slightly higher than their female counterparts.

Research Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in mean performance of Physics concepts between students taught using Guided-Inquiry and those taught with Expository strategies

Table 2.1 Summary of ANCOVA analysis of SS II Students' Performance taught Physics with Guided-Inquiry and those taught with Expository method (n=220).

Source	Type III Sum of Square	Df	Mean Square	F-cal	P-Value	Remark
Pretest	144.89	1	144.89	.930	.336	
Strategy	2534.90	1	2534.90	16.27	.000*	Sig
Residual	33807.49	217	155.80			
Total	869780.00	220				

As shown in Table 2.1, the calculated P-value (.000) is less than the alpha level (.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that exists a significant difference in the mean performance scores of Physics students taught Simple Harmonic Motion using Guided-Inquiry, and Expository methods. The

result suggests that the observed difference in means could be due to random chance rather than a true effect of the treatment or strategy. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected, suggesting a meaningful difference in performance based on instructional strategy.

Research Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in retention of Physics concepts between students taught using Guided-Inquiry and those taught with Expository strategies

Table 2.2 Summary of ANCOVA analysis of SS II Students' Retention taught Physics with Guided-Inquiry and those taught with Expository method (n=220).

Source	Type III Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F-cal	P-Value	Remark
Posttest	320.93	1	320.93	2.214	.138	
Strategy	2391.74	1	2391.74	16.497	.000*	Sign
Residual	31459.95	217	144.98			
Total	626111.00	220				

As shown in Table 2.2, the calculated P-value (.000) is less than the alpha level (.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that exists significant difference in the mean retention scores of Physics students taught Simple Harmonic Motion using Guided-Inquiry, and Expository methods. The result suggests that the observed difference in means retention scores could be unlikely due to random chance and the instructional strategy had effect on students' retention. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Research Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in mean retention scores between the male and female students taught with Guided-Inquiry and Expository laboratory strategies.

Table 2.3 Analysis of Covariance of Students Retention Scores Based on Gender Using Posttest scores as Covariate

Source	Type III Sum of Square	Df	Mean Square	F-cal	P-value	Remark
Posttest	315.49	1	315.49	2.157	.143	
Strategy	2397.63	1	2397.63	16.40	.000*	Sign
Gender	11.97	1	11.97	.082	.775	
Strategy*Gender	20.00	1	20.00	.137	.712	
Residual	31427.23	215	146.17			
Total	34865.43	220				

As shown in Table 2.3 the calculated P-Value (.000) is less than the alpha level (.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there exists a significant difference between the mean retention scores of male and female students Simple Harmonic Motion in Physics when taught using Guided-Inquiry and Expository Methods.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Effect of Guided-Inquiry and Expository method on Academic Performance of Students in Physics

The result of the study indicates significant difference between the mean performance of students taught the concept of Simple Harmonic Motion using Guided-Inquiry and Expository Laboratory Strategies. This outcome suggests that while both instructional approaches may have educational value, one of the strategies outperformed the other significantly in enhancing students' performance in the concept of Simple Harmonic Motion. The findings align with a study conducted by Liadi et al (2024) investigated the comparative effects of Guided-Inquiry and Expository Instructional Strategies on students' academic performance in electricity concept in physics in Kano state, Nigeria. It was observed from the results that students in the guided-inquiry group performed significantly better than those taught using expository methods. The study concluded that expository teaching, while time-efficient, does not adequately engage learners nor foster deep understanding of physics concepts such as electricity. Similarly, Ogunleye (2020) examined the effect of inquiry-based learning compared to expository methods on student achievement and retention in Biology in Ibadan, Oyo State. The results showed that students exposed to inquiry-based strategies significantly outperformed their counterparts taught via traditional lecture methods, both in immediate post-tests and in retention tests administered weeks later. Ogunleye emphasized that the inquiry-based approach stimulated curiosity, critical thinking, and long-term memory, which the expository approach failed to support. In another study, Eze and Okafor (2021) investigated the impact of cooperative learning and expository instruction on Physics achievement among 150 SS2 students in Enugu State. The study utilized a quasi-experimental design, employing pre-test and post-test measures. Students taught through expository means demonstrated poorer engagement, weaker retention, and lower performance scores in post-tests compared to their peers exposed to cooperative and guided learning techniques. These findings support the conclusion of the present study, which revealed that students taught using Guided-Inquiry strategies performed significantly better than those taught with the traditional Expository method. This significant difference may be attributed to the active learning nature of Guided-Inquiry, which encourages student participation, critical thinking, and conceptual understanding. Unlike the more passive Expository approach, Guided-Inquiry allows learners to construct knowledge through exploration and collaboration, making it more effective in teaching abstract topics like Simple Harmonic Motion.

Effect of Guided-Inquiry and Expository method on Students' Retention in Physics

The outcome of this study, which identified a significant difference in retention scores between students taught Simple Harmonic Motion through Guided-Inquiry and Expository strategies, is supported by recent empirical evidence. For example, Okoli and Eze (2021) carried out a quasi-experimental study involving 120 senior secondary school students in Anambra State, comparing the effects of guided-inquiry and lecture-based teaching on retention in Physics. Their findings indicated that students taught via guided-inquiry retained Physics concepts more effectively than those taught through traditional methods, highlighting the long-term value of learner-centered instruction. Likewise, Usman and Bello (2020) conducted a study across six secondary schools in Kano State using a pretest-posttest control group design with 180 participants. Their results demonstrated significantly better retention among students taught using the guided-inquiry method, which they attributed to the interactive and participatory nature of the learning process that enhances information processing and memory. In summary, these studies lend strong support to the present research, suggesting that guided-inquiry facilitates improved cognitive retention through active learning, reflective thinking, and engagement with real-world problem-solving, especially in complex topics like Simple Harmonic Motion.

Effect of Guided-Inquiry and Expository method on Students' Retention in Physics and Gender

The results of this study indicate a significant difference in the mean retention scores between the male and female students taught the concept of Simple Harmonic Motion with Guided-Inquiry and Expository Strategies. The results shows that the male students outperforming their female counterparts in retention of knowledge in both the Guided-Inquiry and Expository instructional strategies. This outcome is consistent with earlier research that highlights gender-based variations in students' cognitive retention in

science disciplines. For example, a study by Ogunleye and Adepoju (2020) in Lagos State examined retention differences in Physics across gender using diverse teaching strategies. Their findings, based on 160 senior secondary students, indicated that male learners demonstrated superior retention, especially in abstract and problem-solving topics. Similarly, Idoko and Oche (2021) explored how gender influenced retention outcomes in Physics among students exposed to activity-based learning in Benue State. Their study also revealed higher retention among male students, which they linked to differences in engagement levels and familiarity with scientific tools. Collectively, these findings reinforce the present study's results and suggest that while innovative teaching methods enhance overall retention, gender-related factors such as motivation, participation, and confidence may significantly influence learning outcomes in Physics.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, the study concluded although guided-inquiry is a student-centered method which is highly recommended in modern days learning, expository method enhanced students' performance and knowledge gain than guided-inquiry method, this could be traceable to some factors. And that there is no disparity between male and female students in any teaching methods.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion drawn, the following recommendations are made to improve students' performance in Physics:

- (i) Physics teachers should utilize and encourage students on the use of student-centered strategies to deliver lesson as it promotes flexible, autonomous and independent learning.
- (ii) Physics teachers should motivate boys and girls to learn effectively to avoid gender disparities in performance and knowledge retention.

REFERENCES

- Ogunleye, A. O., & Ayodele, J. B. (2021). *Enhancing conceptual retention in senior secondary physics through interactive strategies in Nigeria*. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 30(4), 511–520. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10956-021-09901-z>
- Adebayo, O. R., & Oladeji, A. T. (2020). *Instructional strategies and teacher competence as predictors of students' retention in physics concepts in senior secondary schools*. *Nigerian Journal of Science and Educational Research*, 6(2), 95–106.
- Adesoji, F. A., & Jimoh, A. T. (2021). *Effect of guided inquiry and expository teaching strategies on secondary school students' retention in chemistry in Nigeria*. *African Journal of Educational Research*, 25(1), 82–91.
- Yusuf, M. O., & Onasanya, S. A. (2020). *Promoting meaningful learning through inquiry-based strategies in science education*. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Technology*, 22(2), 49–61.
- Eze, G. U., Ofoegbu, T. O., & Ukoha, M. C. (2020). *Effect of guided inquiry instructional approach on students' academic achievement and retention in chemistry*. *Nigerian Journal of Science Education*, 18(1), 45–56.
- Okeke, E. A. C., & John, C. N. (2021). *Bridging the gender gap in STEM education: A critical review of current interventions*. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 8(1), 22–34. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40594-021-00289-2>
- Cheryan, S., Ziegler, S. A., Montoya, A. K., & Jiang, L. (2017). *Why are some STEM fields more gender balanced than others?* *Psychological Bulletin*, 143(1), 1–35. <https://doi.org/10.1037/bul0000052>
- Oladipo, M. O., & Abimbola, I. O. (2020). *Effectiveness of guided discovery instructional strategy on students' achievement in science in Kwara State, Nigeria*. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 11(3), 64–71.

- Adewale, A. S., & Ogunleye, A. O. (2021). *Effect of guided discovery strategy on secondary school students' achievement in basic science across school locations in Nigeria*. *Journal of Science Education and Research*, 7(2), 45–55.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). Sage Publications.
- Almalki, S., & Alghamdi, A. (2023). Gender disparities and potentials in STEM approach in Jordan and Saudi Arabia – An analytical literature review. *Hungarian Educational Research Journal*, 14(2), 217–232.
- Bruner, J. S. (1961). The act of discovery. *Harvard Educational Review*, 31(1), 21–32. <https://doi.org/10.17763/haer.31.1.vjr0234w104a0236>
- Demirci, N. (2017). Effects of computer simulations on higher order thinking skills and attitude towards physics in a blended learning environment. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 70, 500–507.
- Eze, J. U., & Okafor, P. N. (2021). *Impact of cooperative and expository instructional strategies on senior secondary school students' performance in Physics in Enugu State*. *Nigerian Journal of Science Education*, 19(3), 87–96.
- Hake, R. R. (2020). The effectiveness of expository teaching in introductory physics laboratories. *Physical Review Physics Education Research*, 16(1), 010110.
- Hazari, Z. (2021). Promoting diversity and inclusion in physics education: Insights from research. *Physical Review Physics Education Research*, 17(1), 010101.
- Hendrickson, T. L. (2015). Integrating responsible conduct of research education into undergraduate biochemistry and molecular biology laboratory curricula. *Biochemistry and Molecular Biology Education*, 43(2), 68–75. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/bmb.20857>
- Idoko, J. U., & Oche, M. O. (2021). Effects of activity-based instructional strategies on gender and students' retention in senior secondary school Physics in Benue State. *African Journal of Educational Research and Development*, 13(2), 132–141.
- Liadi, M. K., Falau, S. A., & Atadoga, M. M. (2024). *Effect of guided-inquiry and expository instructional strategies on students' academic performance in Physics in Kano State, Nigeria*. *Journal of Science and Technology Education*, 12(1), 33–42.
- Njoku, Z. C. (2007). Comparative effects of guided inquiry and demonstration methods on achievement and interest in chemistry among secondary school students. *Journal of Science Teachers Association of Nigeria*, 42(1), 43–51.
- Nosek, B. A., Smyth, F. L., Sriram, N., Lindner, N. M., Devos, T., Ayala, A., ... Greenwald, A. G. (2009). National differences in gender-science stereotypes predict national sex differences in science and math achievement. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 106(26), 10593–10597.
- Nwoye, A. N., Okeke, S. O. C., & Nwosu, F. C. (2020). Gender and academic retention of secondary school students taught electrostatics with computer animated instructional package in Awka Education Zone. *UNIZIK Journal of STM Education*, 3(2), 41–50.
- Ogunleye, A. O. (2020). *Comparative effects of inquiry-based and expository teaching methods on students' achievement and retention in Biology in Oyo State, Nigeria*. *African Journal of Educational Research*, 24(2), 102–115.
- Ogunleye, A. O., & Adepoju, O. O. (2020). Exploring gender variation in Physics achievement and retention using guided-discovery method in Lagos State. *Nigerian Journal of Science Education*, 18(1), 65–73.
- Okoli, E. C., & Eze, J. U. (2021). Impact of guided-inquiry and lecture methods on secondary school students' retention in Physics in Anambra State. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Research and Evaluation*, 20(2), 75–83.
- Prince, M. (2021). Does active learning work? A review of the research. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 110(4), 516–553.

- Sadeh, I., & Zion, M. (2021). Teaching with expository labs: Conceptual understanding and scientific inquiry. *Research in Science Education*, 51(2), 435–451.
- Sam, U. E., & Stephen, U. U. (2025). PhET simulation and gender on students' academic performance in Physics. *International Journal of Research in Education and Sustainable Development*, 5(5), 25–37. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15754315>
- Singh, C. (2020). Supporting educational transformation in a large-enrollment physics course: The benefits of an active learning approach. *Physical Review Physics Education Research*, 16(1), 010112.
- Udo, M. E., & Udofia, A. E. (2021). Comparative effects of expository and problem-solving methods on students' achievement in senior secondary school Physics. *Nigerian Journal of Science Education*, 5(1), 48–56.
- UNESCO. (2023). New UNESCO report sheds light on gender inequality in STEM education. *UNESCO*. <https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/new-unesco-report-sheds-light-gender-inequality-stem-education>
- Usman, S. A., & Bello, R. A. (2020). Comparative study of guided-inquiry and conventional teaching methods on students' retention in Physics. *African Journal of Educational Studies in Mathematics and Sciences*, 16(1), 92–101.
- Wang, M.-T., & Degol, J. L. (2017). Gender gap in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM): Current knowledge, implications for practice, policy, and future directions. *Educational Psychology Review*, 29(1), 119–140.